

EBFMC25-OP-91 · Palliative Support Approaches in Patients with Severe Head and Maxillofacial Trauma

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study aims to evaluate the role of palliative support therapy in patients with severe head and maxillofacial trauma (HMT) and to examine the relationship between clinical course, end-of-life care decisions, and prognosis.

Materials and Methods: Between January 2022 and December 2024, 16 patients diagnosed with severe head and maxillofacial trauma and having a Glasgow Coma Score ≤ 8 were retrospectively analyzed in a tertiary care center. Palliative interventions such as advanced life support, pain management, ventilator therapy, and symptom control were assessed in all patients. Demographic data, trauma mechanism, CT findings, timing of palliative intervention, and intensive care unit duration were recorded.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 54.6 ± 18.3 years, and 68.7% were male. The most common trauma mechanism was falling from height (43.7%). The average Glasgow Coma Score was 5. In patients where palliative support decisions were made within the first 72 hours of intensive care, analgesia, sedation, and limitation of invasive procedures were prioritized. End-of-life care was planned for 62.5% (10 out of 16) patients. The mean duration of intensive care was 8.7 ± 3.4 days, with a survival rate of 18.7%.

Conclusion: Palliative support therapy plays a critical role in ensuring non-invasive symptom control and patient comfort in severe HMT patients (Fernando & Hughes, 2019). Early multidisciplinary evaluation and end-of-life care planning in this patient group are crucial in preventing unnecessary interventions.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Head trauma, maxillofacial trauma, palliative care, end-of-life, intensive care, symptom management

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Fernando, G., & Hughes, S. (2019). Team approaches in palliative care: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Palliative Nursing*, 25(9), 444–450. <https://doi.org/10.12968/ijpn.2019.25.9.444>

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